

CULTURAL SUSTAINABILITY WITH THE RE-FUNCTIONING OF THE FIRDEVES BEY BEDESTEN STRUCTURE IN ISPARTA

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This study does not require ethics committee approval.

Abstract. Restoring historical structures with material and spiritual value that have lost their functionality is a crucial method of preservation. Bedestens, which served as central elements of urban planning during the Ottoman period and encompassed various functions, have largely diminished in their former significance and utility. Consequently, it is essential to assign these structures suitable new functions while considering socio-cultural, environmental, and economic factors. Firdevs Bey Bedesten, located in the Isparta province of Türkiye, has significantly lost its functionality and importance, despite still serving its original purpose. This study examines the historical and architectural features of this monumental bedesten and analyses its current status in terms of structure, functionality, and aesthetics. By considering the usage patterns of other bedestens from the Ottoman period, a new functional proposal was developed for Firdevs Bey Bedesten to enhance its functionality, recognition, and urban and monumental quality. The proposal includes a spatial layout, technical equipment, furniture, and material selection for the proposed exhibition and event hall, which was visualized through a three-dimensional model study. This work aims to provide an exhibition and event hall that is currently lacking in Isparta province, while also adapting the building to modern conditions and preserving its historical significance for future generations.

Keywords: Ottoman bazaars, cultural sustainability, sustainable re-functioning, historical preservation, conservation, historical identity

Introduction

The term "bedesten" originates from Persian words that refer to a marketplace for trading cloth, clothing, or weapons. In Arabian, Iranian, and East Asian contexts, bezzazistan structures are referred to as inside the castle "kaysariyya" (Akar, 2009).

Bedestens are traditional Turkish commercial structures used for merchants' sales, such as arasta, covered bazaars, and shops. These structures were constructed during the later years of the Anatolian Seljuk Empire and expanded throughout the Second Anatolian Principality. The functions and characteristics of bedestens evolved under the Ottoman Empire, increasing their significance and quantity (İnan, 1996).

Bedestens, where cloth and fabric sales occurred in the early eras, became the most important architectural structure in cities during the Ottoman period (Karacalı, 2019). Located near the "ulu mosques" (central mosques), which served as the religious headquarters in Ottoman cities, bedestens formed the core of the trade zone. Eyice (1992), İnan (1996), and Akar (2009) reported that commercial buildings are situated around bedestens based on the value of their goods.

During the foundational period of the Ottoman Empire, bedestens emerged in the capitals and underwent continuous structural and functional developments. This evolution led to their construction throughout the country in the 15th and 16th centuries (Akar, 2009; İntepe, 2006). These venues facilitated key activities such as stock exchanges, tax offices, banking, business management and marketplaces, as exemplified by the Istanbul Bedesten. Consequently, bedestens flourished particularly in cities where trade was prominent (Ergün, 2020; Şimşek, 2020). Evliya Çelebi's classification of Ottoman cities into "cities with bedestens" and "cities without bedestens" in his "Seyahatname" underscores the significance of bedestens as indicators of the commercial development of cities (İnan, 1996; Karacalı, 2019). The structures and commercial significance of the bedestens greatly impressed European travellers who visited the Ottoman Empire. Salomon Schweigger (2004) noted the bedestens during his journey, stating, 'Istanbul also has a beautiful commercial building in which all kinds of expensive goods are found. These items come from distant countries and are skill fully processed in Istanbul'. Hans Dernschwam (1992) described bedestens as follows: 'There are two large bazaars known as bedesten. These are the most beautiful and luxurious bedesten in Istanbul. Various silk fabrics from all countries are offered to guests by sellers of diverse nationalities'. Heath W. Lowry (2004), during his visit to Bursa, remarked on the bedestens, saying, 'The bedesten in the city of Bursa was a well-constructed and imposing building. Inside, there were large shops and warehouses reminiscent of those in the Palais in Paris. In addition to goods produced in this region, all the products of the Eastern Mediterranean can be found here.'. Depictions of various bedestens are illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1. a – Sandal Bedesten, Istanbul (Anonymous Greek artist, 1809); b – Grand Bazaar, Istanbul (Millingen, 1906)

When evaluating bedestens, which have been among the most significant civil architectural structures from the past to the present, it becomes evident that many have lost their utility and historical significance. The area under study, Firdevs Bey Bedesten in Türkiye's Isparta province, has also diminished in density and importance, despite retaining its original function. This study aims to refunction this monumental structure, which holds significant urban and historical value, and restore it as a point of attraction.

Bedestens from an Architectural Perspective

Although some authors refer to bedestens as Turkish kaysariyya, Eyice (1992) explains that bedestens are constructions with traditional Turkish architecture in terms of both function and structural style. These structures, which are typically created in each city to form the main centre of the city, along with the grand mosques, form the primary cluster of the city and signify its Ottoman heritage.

Bedestens were originally built as timber constructions. However, their transition into areas where vital roles took place over time required the use of safe and lasting materials, and they were built with a cut stone or stone-brick mixed plan (Halaç & Ergün, 2020). Typically, bedestens are square or rectangular constructions. The roofs of these constructions with high ceilings are typically covered with lead to protect them from rain and snow. To ensure security, the number and size of openings, such as doors and windows are regulated. The windows are iron-capped and located at high altitudes. The doors on one, two, or four sides of the structure are high and made of iron or ebony wood (Tuluk & Üstün, 2007; Kuzucular, 2013). The vaults and domes are typically built of brick, whereas arches are formed from cut stone or brick (Tuluk & Üstün, 2007). The architecture of bedestens that store valuable goods and documents depends on ideas of durability, longevity, enclosure and security.

When the inner layout of the bedestens is examined, it is clear that the shops are typically aligned parallel to the exterior walls. In the main bedestens, they are arranged parallel to the inner walls (İntepe, 2006; Kuzucular, 2013).

Although there are no clear boundaries, bedestens are categorized into six classes according to the type of floor plan: "simple bedesten," "bedesten with cellar," "bedesten with external shops," "floor bedesten," "arasta bedesten," and "bedesten with arasta" (Figure 2) (Ergün, 2020).

Figure 2. Turkish bedestens according to the type of floor plan (Tuluk & Üstün, 2007)

Material

The research area focused on the monumental Firdevs Bey Bedesten, which dates from the Ottoman period and is located in Kaymakkapı Square, Isparta, Türkiye (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Location of the Study Area (Google Earth, n.d.)

The Üzümlü Pazarı, a historical bazaar designated as an "urban site," is located on the north side of Firdevs Bey Bedesten. To the east, you will find the government building and Ulu (Kutlubey) Mosque; to the south are the Dalboyunoglu (New) Hamam and Bey Hamam; and to the west are the Municipality Business Centre and the old Isparta Hotel (now known as Iyaspark Hotel), which was the city's first hotel.

The area surrounding the bazaar is also home to buildings from both the Ottoman and Republican periods, as well as Atatürk Park, a city park. This region has been officially designated as a "historical site" (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Surroundings of the Study Area (Demokrat32 Gazetesi, 2024; Google Earth, n.d.)

The building located in the Kutlubey Neighborhood on Bedesten Street in Isparta was originally constructed as a bedesten. Although some of its commercial spaces have changed over time, it has generally retained its original functions.

Resarch Findings

Firdevs Bey Bedesten was established by the governor of the time, Firdevs Bey, to generate income for the Mimar Sinan Mosque (The Governorship of Isparta, 2009). The official sources indicate that the construction of the bedesten occurred in 1561. Bayrakal (2015), asserts that the two-door masonry bedesten was reconstructed based on a foundation charter dated 1565-1566. However, the original construction date of the Firdevs Bey Bedesten, which lacks an inscription, remains uncertain in the sources.

The structure, designed in the Mimar Sinan style, was constructed to accommodate 30-60 cabinets and shops on opposite sides. In 1822, the bedesten, having lose its commercial value, was closed and repurposed as a warehouse (Gökçe, 2016; Bayrakal, 2015). In 1967, wooden partitions were installed to create shops within the building, and it was returned to service. The lead-coated barrel vault was replaced and replaced with a wooden roof. In the 1990s, the roof was restored to its original state by being covered with lead (The Governorship of Isparta, 2009). However, during the restoration in 2009, it was converted to a tile roof (Figure 5) (Türkiye Cultural Portal, 2024).

Figure 5. a – Lead-coated roof of the bedesten (Gedik et al.,2010) b – The wooden-tiled roof of the bedesten (İhlas Haber Ajansı, 2022)

The structure was registered by the High Council for the Historical Real Estate and Monuments on May 13, 1977, under the registration number A-548. The Antalya Cultural and Natural Heritage Protection Regional Board continued the registration on September 25, 1990, assigning it the number 901 (The Governorship of Isparta, 2009).

Firdevs Bey Bedesten is a masonry structure characterized by its entrance facades constructed from cut stones, while the side facades are made of rubble stones and regional kofke stone (The Governorship of Isparta, 2009). The building has a rectangular shape, extending in a north-south orientation. This elongated, narrow construction is comprised of a single volume and lacks internal walls. The interior, there are 12 shops arranged in two rows, separated by wooden partitions that face each other. The arched entrance doors are equipped with folding wrought iron gates on both narrow sides, each featuring a rectangular window above. The roof, which is topped with a barrel vault, is covered with corrugated tiles.

The Bedesten features a rectangular layout measuring 9.8 by 28.8 metres, with a side facade height of 5.7 metres and a roof ridge height of 8.1 metres. The load-bearing walls are 130 cm thick. The two arches divide the structure into three equal sections and support a vaulted ceiling. Additionally, there are nine wooden supports, each 4.2 metres tall and approximately 3 m apart, which enhance the structural stability (Figure 6).

Figure 6. a – Firdevs Bey Bedesten Registration Form (The Governorship of Isparta, 2009); b – The plans and elevations of Firdevs Bey Bedesten (Gedik et al., 2010)

Current Situation Analysis

Structural analysis

The existing load-bearing system of the Firdevs Bey Bedesten is in a good condition. In order to reduce the load on the roof, previous structural elements, which included irregular granular fill and a thick concrete layer from earlier restorations, were removed. The roof, originally covered with lead, was replaced with a wooden and tiled structure. During the restoration, efforts were made to remove some incorrect repairs that had been executed using inappropriate materials, although some could not be addressed. The aim was to use materials compatible with the original design. However, the evidence suggests that incomplete and improper repairs were conducted.

Moss and deterioration developed on the facade of the bedesten due to moisture from rainwater (Figure 7). To mitigate these issues, it is essential to ensure that water is drained from building surfaces and to maintain the roof and gargoyles while addressing any existing problems.

Figure 7. Moss and deterioration on the facade of the bedesten

Although there are folding wrought iron doors at both entrances of the building, they are non-operational and not in use. The bedesten is protected by unattractive automatic shutters (Figure 8). Reusing doors that are suitable for the building and reflective of the historical period will enhance the building's integrity.

Figure 8. Entrance gate of Firdevs Bey Bedesten

Firdevs Bey Bedesten suffers from inadequate natural lighting, a consequence of the security concerns prevalent during its construction. The number and size of the openings were intentionally limited, resulting in a significant issue regarding natural lighting problem. The building has two entrances and two windows; however, these do not sufficiently address lighting needs. Consequently, artificial lighting is employed, including wall lamps mounted on the front sections of the wooden partitioned shops in the main circulation area, as well as chandelier lights from the ceiling. In addition, the chandeliers and the localised lighting in the display cases have been used in the shops (Figure 9). Overall, there is a lack of coherent planning and integration of lighting design.

Figure 9. Artificial lighting elements of the bedesten

There is no fire system in the area that serves as the main circulation and passageway of the venue. Additionally, there is no mechanical ventilation system in the place. Airflow to the interior is facilitated by parallel door openings that remain open during operating hours, as well as the gaps created by the windows above these doors. The glass in the centre of the windows have been removed to reduce moisture accumulation in the shops when the bedesten is closed (Figure 10).

Figure 10. Openings that facilitate natural lighting and ventilation in the bedesten

The structure lacks a centralised heating and cooling system; each shop is equipped with individual air conditioning and heating units. The constant opening of the entrances during the bedesten's operational hours presents an additional challenge to the implementation of a centralized heating and cooling system. Furthermore, there is no water installation in the structure, as it does not contain any wet areas.

Functional analysis

Although Firdevs Bey Bedesten is a monumental structure that retains its original function, it fails to accommodate the requirements of modern commercial spaces. This limitation restricts the installation of equipment, furniture, and other preferences. As a result, the traders within the bedesten struggle to display and store their products effectively. Due to the lack of a designated storage area in the shops, boxes are often seen stacked on the ceilings of the workplaces. Some traders are required to rent additional shops solely for storage purposes.

The utilisation of the hall, serves as the sole communal space of the bedesten, for the presentation of merchandise has the effect flow of pedestrian traffic. This area, serving as the entrance, exit, and main circulation axis of the bedesten, also functions as a street or passageway. Consequently, this situation results in an insufficient circulation area that does not adequately meet the needs of visitors (Figure 11). Furthermore, the steps at the entrance hinder barrier-free access to the space.

Figure 11. Problems with product display and storage in the bedesten

Aesthetic analysis

In addition to the storage and display of products in front of the shops, the haphazard arrangement of various styles, types, and colours of furniture -such as cabinets, tables, and consoles- creates an unappealing aesthetic. The

juxtaposition of modern ceiling chandeliers with rustic wall lamps further contributes to this visual discord. Additionally, the heating and cooling devices utilized by the shops, in the absence of central heating, cooling, or ventilation, detract from the overall visual experience and pose potential safety hazard.

The presence of visual pollution elements, such as satellite dishes and cables on the exterior of the building, detracts from its historical value. Additionally, the exterior has been subjected to vandalism. One factor contributing to the negative perception of the facade is the poorly designed workplace signs. The current placement of these signs should be reconsidered; they ought to be designed independently of the building while harmonizing with its identity. Furthermore, the signage for the bedesten should be crafted to complement the building's texture, which will positively influence the visual perception of this monumental structure (Figure 12).

Figure 12. Factors that detract from the visual appeal of the bedesten

Current Functions of Ottoman Period Bedestens

Changes in sociocultural, economic, and environmental factors necessitate the adaptation of old buildings for new functions. To make these buildings fit modern needs, they need to be renovated, which is called re-functionalization (Kaşlı, 2008; Ergün, 2020). The re-functionalisation of monumental structures facilitates their contemporary use through various adaptations while simultaneously preserving the spiritual values they embody. This ensures that the structures remain liveable and guarantees their transfer to future generations (Kaşlı, 2008).

Similar to global practices, structures of both material and spiritual significance are deemed worthy of preservation in our country. Recently, re-functionalization has gained prominence as a conservation method aimed at ensuring the continuity of structures and cities, enhancing the city's image, and increasing societal historical awareness (Sezgin Özrili, 2020).

An investigation into the bedestens from the Ottoman period that have survived to the present day reveals the existence of 50 examples of these structures. The analysis of the functions of these bedestens indicates that they serve a variety of purposes, encompassing both cultural and commercial roles (Table 1).

Table 1. Ottoman period bedestens that have survived to the present day and their current functions

<i>Current Function</i>	<i>Name of the Bedesten</i>	<i>Location</i>
<i>Idle building</i>	Kütahya Küçük Bedesten	Kütahya
	Şumnu Bedesten	Bulgaria
<i>During the restoration</i>	Kozan Bedesten	Adana
	Beyşehir Bedesten	Konya
	Bergama Bedesten	İzmir
	Pamukçu Bedesten	Safranbolu
	Yenişehir (Larissa) Bedesten	Greece
<i>Bazaar</i>	Cevahir Bedesten	İstanbul
	Firdevs Bey Bedesten	Isparta
	Konya Bedesten	Konya
	Amasya Bedesten	Amasya
	Gümüşhacıköy Bedesten	Amasya
	Kahramanmaraş Bedesten	Kahramanmaraş
	Edirne Bedesten	Edirne
	Adana (Seyhan) Bedesten	Adana
	Zincirli Bedesten	Gaziantep

	Kemikli Bedesten	Gaziantep
	Kayseriyye Bedesten	Mardin
	Trabzon Bedesten	Trabzon
	Kütahya Büyük Bedesten	Kütahya
	Afyonkarahisar Bedesten	Afyonkarahisar
	Rüstem Paşa Bedesten	Tekirdağ
	Vezirköprü Bedesten	Samsun
	Selanik Bedesten	Greece
	Gazi Hüseyin Bedesten	Bosnia and Herzegovina
	Üsküp Bedesten	Makedonia
	Yanbolu Bedesten	Bulgaria
	Galata Bedesten	İstanbul
	Yıldırım Bayezid Bedesten	Bursa
	Camlı Bedesten	Balıkesir
	Kayseri Bedesten	Kayseri
	Taşhan Rüstem Paşa Bedesten	Erzurum
	Kızlarağası Çuha Bedesten	İzmir
	Kırkaşık Bedesten	Tarsus
	Hızır Bey Bedesten	Kırklareli
	Sokullu Mehmet Paşa Bedesten	Niğde
	Bayburt	Bayburt Bedesteni
	Kazzaz Bedesten	Şanlıurfa
	Uşak Bedesten	Uşak
<i>Hotel</i>	Alanya Bedesten	Alanya
<i>Restaurant-Cafe</i>	Merzifon Bedesten	Merzifon
	Cem Sultan Bedesten	Kastamonu
	Sandal Bedesten	İstanbul
<i>Wedding and multipurpose hall</i>	Rum Mehmet Paşa Bedesten	Manisa
<i>Exhibition multipurpose hall</i>	İştîp Bedesten	Makedonia
	Lefkoşa (Bandabulya) Bedesten	Cyprus
	Tire Bedesten	İzmir
<i>Museum</i>	Mahmut Paşa Bedesten	Ankara
	Tokat Bedesten	Tokat
	Serez Bedesten	Greece

An examination of the bedesten from the Ottoman period reveals that 2% are used as hotels, 2% serve as wedding halls, 4% are idle, 6% function as exhibition and multipurpose halls, 6% are designated as museums, 6% operate as food and beverage venues, 10% are undergoing restoration, and 64% remain as traditional bazaars (Figure 13).

Figure 13. Function of Ottoman Bedestens today

Functional proposal for Firdevs Bey Bedesten

An examination of the surviving bedestens from the Ottoman period reveals that the majority continue to serve commercial purposes. However, considering the needs of the city of Isparta, the location of the Firdevs Bey Bedesten, and the analyses conducted, it is evident that the most suitable function for this structure would be as a cultural and artistic exhibition hall.

The facilitation of public engagement with cultural and artistic activities represents a pivotal aspect of urban development. Exhibition spaces fulfil this mission by creating an environment where the relationship between space and objects is established for the viewing, perception, and selection of cultural and artistic works, ultimately

presenting them to the public. In the Isparta Province, cultural and artistic exhibitions are typically held in venues with a variety of functions, including educational institutions, shopping malls, public institutions, and historical residences. The fact that the sole purpose of these exhibitions is not merely to display art has a detrimental impact on the quality of the exhibitions and the perception of the works. The strategic location of the Firdevs Bey Bedesten in the city square, the most central point of Isparta, combined with its function as a corridor connecting streets, will facilitate access to exhibitions for a larger audience.

In transforming the Firdevs Bey Bedesten for its new function, the existing wooden partitions that create individual shops will be removed, thereby revealing the main mass of the structure. This undivided, rectangular main structure, featuring doors on each of the two short sides, encompasses an area of 282 m², providing an ideal space for exhibitions and other cultural activities. The structure's height of 5.7 metres at its lowest point creates a spacious environment with a high ceiling, positively supports to its exhibition function.

The natural masonry texture of the building will enhance both the cultural and historical value of the exhibition space and the presentation quality of the artworks. While the structure's limitations in natural lighting present challenges for its current function, they also create an ideal situation for exhibition spaces by preventing artwork from being perceived or damaged.

A double-circulation, comb-type circulation area was established in the new interior design of the Firdevs Bey Bedesten. The two-dimensional works are exhibited in a linear arrangement parallel to the outer wall, while the panels are grouped in the centre to facilitate the circulation and viewing of the artworks. In front of the structural columns, pedestals have been placed for the display of three-dimensional works (Figure 14).

Figure 14. Firdevs Bey Bedesten exhibition hall general views

The functional furniture between the panel groups is designed to serve as a seating or for showcasing product. To preserve the historical integrity of the structure during the exhibition, free-standing panels were chosen. Additionally, the portability of these panels allows for flexible use of space. Artificial lighting has been primarily utilized in lighting design, allowing for optimal emphasis on exhibited products through localised illumination. The rail system spotlights were selected to ensure that neither the artwork nor the structure was damaged and to allow for adjustments based on the location of the works. The rail systems have been installed in two rows in order to accommodate the spatial configuration and the positioning of the exhibition units. Rustic wrought iron chandeliers have been positioned in a row in the centre of the building, complemented by local lighting to enhance brightness, when necessary, while aligning with the historical identity of the building (Figure 15).

Figure 15. Firdevs Bey Bedesten exhibition hall interior design

The design of the space includes a consultation area, a waiting area, and a cocktail area situated apart from the designated main exhibition zone. The building features two entrances, with a small consultation area created at each entrance for control and information purposes, and a waiting area located opposite. In the centre of the area, a cocktail space has been designed for hosting small events, fostering a conducive environment for gatherings (Figure 16).

Figure 16. Firdevs Bey Bedesten exhibition hall entrance and cocktail area

Conclusions

The survival, preservation, and sustainability of architectural structures are fundamentally contingent upon their usage conditions, particularly their functionality. As urban environments evolve due to economic, social, cultural, and environmental transformations, there arises an imperative need to re-evaluate the functions attributed to historical buildings. This adaptation of cultural assets is crucial not only for safeguarding their monumental values but also for ensuring their transmission to future generations.

Historically, bedestens held a significant role in the urban planning of the Ottoman Empire, serving as critical nodes in trade and commerce. However, many of these structures, including the Firdevs Bey Bedesten, have markedly diminished in their functional capacities over time. While the Firdevs Bey Bedesten continues to operate as a commercial space, it has experienced a considerable decline in both functionality and relevance in the contemporary context. A thorough analysis of the current situation identifies several challenges that compromise the bedesten's commercial viability and its monumental identity. These issues inhibit the structure's ability to meet modern user needs while simultaneously detracting from its historical significance.

In response to these challenges, this study proposes a strategic refunctioning of the Firdevs Bey Bedesten to ensure its preservation and renewed relevance. It is posited that utilizing the bedesten as a cultural and artistic exhibition space would be a more fitting adaptation, taking into consideration the functional requirements of the city of Isparta, the structure's central location, and its unique architectural features. A redesign of the structure aimed at this purpose has been developed.

Although the bedesten may not adequately serve the demands of contemporary commercial spaces, it possesses favorable conditions suited for exhibition purposes. By dismantling the existing wooden partitions within the bedesten, the primary mass and texture of the masonry structure are accentuated, revealing its architectural integrity. The resulting undivided rectangular space, characterized by a high ceiling and entry points on both short ends, creates an optimal environment for the display of exhibitions and a variety of cultural activities. While the limitation of natural light may pose a challenge for certain modern functions, it offers advantages in protecting exhibited works from potential damage due to environmental factors.

The proposed design for the exhibition space is carefully conceived to respect the historical structure while allowing for flexible use. An innovative lighting design has been incorporated to maximize the adaptability of space utilization while safeguarding the integrity of the monumental structure.

It is anticipated that this newly envisioned function will substantially enhance the monumental identity of the Firdevs Bey Bedesten, establishing it as a pivotal cultural landmark. The building's strategic location and condition are poised to facilitate the dissemination of cultural and artistic endeavors to a broader audience. Moreover, this refunctioning is expected to contribute significantly to the artistic and cultural enrichment of the city, fortifying its historical connections and elevating the overall perception of Isparta.

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